

Original Research Article

Mental Stress of COVID-19 Pandemic and Lockdown among Nursing Students and Staff of University of Lahore

Nargis Mansha, Muhammad Hussain, Muhammad Afzal, Syed Amir Gilani

Abstract

¹BS Nursing, Lahore School of Nursing,, The University of Lahore, PO Box 54000, Lahore, Pakistan.

²Assistant Professor, Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore, PO Box 54000, Lahore, Pakistan.

³Associate Professor, Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore, PO Box 54000, Lahore, Pakistan.

⁴Professor, FAHS, The University of Lahore, PO Box 54000, Lahore, Pakistan.

*Corresponding Author E-mail:
nargismansha700@gmail.com
mughalnargis782@gmail.com
Tel: +92(0)4235321
Fax: +924235321
Mobile Phone: 03054043300

Coronavirus (COVID-19) firstly appeared in China in 2019 as a deadly disease which gradually encompassed the whole world. For its prevention, a nationwide quarantine and lockdown was suggested and applied in many countries which had great impact not only on the general public and educational system but all the systems of the world psychologically. It could be observed that the ratio of psychological impact i.e. stress, anxiety and depression varies among people related to different factors. The students and the workers of university especially of the medical staff influenced by this pandemic much more. Nationwide lockdown affected the study and created emotional disturbance of uncertainty as no one knows how and when all the things and classes will go on previous routine. I will hereby evaluate the ratio and frequency of psychological impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the medical students, workers and university staff. For this purpose, a questionnaire based survey will be conducted from 150 participants including the nursing staff, students and medical students as well as university faculty members and workers. The results will be compiled by the method and will be analysed by using standard tools. The aim of this study will be to find the factors so that it will be easy to manage the mental health affecting factors in early stages and prevent the population of university from psychological issues. Covid19 is a very threatening and alarming condition all over the world. It has affected worldwide social, economic and mental health of the people, because of coronavirus people are afraid of going outside, afraid to moot anyone, afraid to continue their job as they perform their work before. At the same time corona affected most of the students' lives because during the corona pandemic students cannot attend their physical classes on campus. That is why the online system introduced is totally unfavourable and most of the students are mentally disturbed due to this pandemic. Nursing students and staff are highly affected due to this pandemic because they have to perform their clinical duties in hospital. The objective is to evaluate the psychological effects of COVID-19 outbreak and lockdown among students and workers of university. This study is a cross-sectional to investigate the mental stress of students and nursing staff during the lockdown of corona pandemic data was analysed on the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. The results showed that many of the respondents had no effect of covid19 pandemic but on the other hand many of the people are badly affected by this pandemic on their mental and social health. This research concludes that most of the people that are affected by this coronavirus are highly disparate while some of the people are not affected.

Keywords: COVID-19, Medical university staff, Mental health, Psychological impact

INTRODUCTION

In indefinite cases of pneumonia in December 2019 detected firstly in Chinese in the city of Wuhan, Hubei

province, China novel coronavirus had been found as an etiological agent (Zhu et al., 2020). Afterward, it gradually

spreads to countries in the European and American continents all over the world and takes the form of pandemic disease. In Turkey, the 1st case of Covid-19 was reported on 11 March 2020 and the rate of patients leads to 90,980 cases on 20 April 2020 along with 2,140 deaths (Özdin and Bayrak Özdin, 2020) On 5th April 2020 130,759 cases were reported in Spain and marked as the third affected country with pandemic. (Odriozola-González et al., 2020) The cases of confirmed COVID increases rapidly along with death rate and according to an estimate 1,200,000 cases were reported all over the world and 68,000 patients had died till 5th April 2020 (Medicine, 2020).

Although, the individuals with the age group of 60s and already suffering with any chronic disease were at greater risk to be exposed to the COVID-19 pandemic than others (Zhou et al., 2020). As the circumstances got worse day by day, governments of different states all over the world declared the closure of schools, universities and population lockdowns. Moreover, they declared it as an emergency alert nationwide which influenced the medical practitioners as well as put a noticeable impact on the general population emotionally. It created the symptoms of stress, depression and anxiety in common peoples leading to adverse mental health problems because it was the 1st time for all to face such an uncertain emergency condition and fight with an imperceptible agent. (Kang et al., 2020; Read, 2004; Shigemura et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020)

As the pandemic affected the educational system almost in the whole world and according to the UNESCO assessment 890 million in 114 countries. More than 160 countries in the world imposed nationwide lockdown or closure which caused educational disruption in 87% of the population of students in the world. New routine of online classes started for students by many universities which imposed another challenge for students as well as for workers. Because all the students were not able to avail such facilities and posed inequality among students. (FVG, 2020; UNESCO, 2020) Peoples feel insecure and remain thinking about death due to certain particulars related to the pandemic i.e. when it will go away or when it will be treated with proper medications or vaccines. Furthermore, the all-time breaking news about the pandemic, its patient's ratio, death ratio and the instructions to stay home, keep social distance etc. put lots of pressure on one's mental health. During the COVID-19 pandemic a number of cases that had symptoms of anxiety, fear, stress, depression, sleeping disorders were found. (Harvey, 2006) In the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) epidemic 10%-18% cases of depression, anxiety and post-traumatic stress disorders were reported. (Wu et al., 2005) From 1 of the regions of china affected by the pandemic (COVID-19) about 7 % peoples were presented with post-traumatic stress symptoms just after 1 month of outbreak (Karoly and Ruehlman, 2006) while 53% peoples presented

feelings of terror. (Zhang and Ma, 2020).

Purpose of Study

Many of the studies have been held showing that inadequate hand cleanliness and not wearing a mask can lead to an increase in infection. This has been due to poor attitude and practices of hand cleanliness and mask wearing. Therefore, this study is being done for assessing the attitude and practices of the Children in the community.

Research Question

What is the COVID-19 effect on the mental health of nursing students?

What is the COVID-19 effect on the mental health of nursing staff?

Conceptual Definitions

COVID-19

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus (WHO).

Significance

This study will help us find out the factors that help to minimize the mental health problem during the Pandemic. This study will help us find out the factors that are leading more and more people towards COVID and will also help us to find the attitude of the community towards it. So that we can arrange awareness for university students and nursing staff and educate them on the right methods so everyone can stay safe during this Pandemic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Material and Method

Study Design

It will be a cross sectional study.

Study Area

The study will be conducted in the vicinity of University of Lahore, Pakistan.

Study Collection Technique

This will be questionnaire based study in which a questionnaire form will be filled by the community of university members, faculty and students of the medical department.

Duration of Study

The duration of study will constitute about 4 months, from 28 September to 15 December.

Sampling Technique

Convenient (non-probability) sampling technique.

Sampling Unit

Students, workers and members of university teams of all age groups and belonging to the medical field will be included from University of Lahore, Pakistan.

Sample Size

150 participants having any history of contact, disease in themselves or their relatives and having concern about COVID-19 in the University of Lahore, Pakistan will participate in this study.

Sample Collection

Inclusion Criteria

- Nursing student
- Nursing staff
- Medical students and professionals

Exclusion Criteria

All the students of different departments other than medical will be excluded from the concerned study.

Data Collection Procedure

A questionnaire will be shaped including all the demographic questions related to their basic information, past history of illness from 14 days, contact history, knowledge and concern about having disease and about preventive measures for this pandemic. This questionnaire will be circled among the participants. They

will fill it on their behalf willingly. Furthermore, consent will be taken from the participants to allow me to use this data in my study and publish it.

Equipment

No specific instrument will be used in this for any evaluation. All the data will be analysed using an appropriate _____ technique as well as using a SPSS latest version statistical tool for statistical analysis. Mean and standard deviations will calculate for all the numerical or quantitative variables such as age, class group and grade. Percentage and value of peoples having the psychological impact by the pandemic outbreak will also be calculated. To express data including percentage, value and frequency graphs, components and multiple bar charts and pie charts will be used.

Ethical Consideration

All information of the participants will be collected, confidentiality permission will be taken before collecting the form from our community and consent will be signed before we start collecting data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study the students of university of Lahore and staff of university of Lahore teaching hospital are included while the students of other disciplines are excluded. After getting data from these respondents we find that 38% male participated in research while 62% female participated. There are 51.33% people falling in the 18-26 age group and there are 48.66% people that are from the age group 26-35. there are 40% administrative staff participating in research and 60% students. There are 51.33% students from first year, 38% from second year and 10.66% from third year. 56% of people participating in research are from hospitals and 44% of people are from university. From which 66.66% are single and 33.33% are married.

In COVID19 outbreak there were 40% administrative staff and 60% students participating in research data collection. There are 44% health workers and 66% are not health workers. There are 19.33% participants live alone, 48.67% participants live with one person, 26.67% participants live with 2-4 persons and 5.33% participants live with 5 or more people. 24% participants have changes in employment, 44% participants have no changes in employment while 32% participants have no employment. There are 44.67% participants tested for covid19 and 55.33% participants are not tested for covid19. There are 33.33% participants reported for covid19 and 65.67% participants are not reported for

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Gender	Male	57(38%)
	Female	93(62%)
	Total	150(100%)
Age	18-26	77(51.33%)
	26-35	73(48.66%)
	Total	150(100%)
Group of respondents	Administrative staff	60(40%)
	Student	90(60%)
	Total	150(100%)
Year of study	1 st	77(51.33%)
	2 nd	57(38%)
	3 rd	16(10.66%)
	Total	150(100%)
Area of study	Hospital	84(56%)
	University	66(44%)
	Total	150(100%)
Marital status	single	100(66.66%)
	Married	50(33.33%)

Table 2. Mental Stress of COVID-19 Pandemic and Lockdown among Nursing Students and Staff

Group of respondent	Administrative staff	40%
	student	60%
	Total	100%
Health worker	Yes	44%
	No	56%
	Total	100%
Live with	Alone	19.33%
	One person	48.67%
	2-4 person	26.67%
	5 or more	5.33%
	Total	100%
Changes in employment	Yes	24%
	No	44%
	No employment	32%
	Total	100%
Tested for covid-19	Yes	44.67%
	No	55.33%
	Total	100%
Reported for covid-19	Yes	33.33%
	No	66.67%
	Total	100%
Known patient with covid-19	Yes	36%
	No	64%
	Total	100%
Symptoms for covid-19	No symptoms	51.33%
	Mild	48.67%
	Total	100%
Previous psychological treatment	Yes	42.67%
	No	57.33%
Current psychological treatment	Total	100%
	Yes	52.33%
Current intake of psychoactive medication	No	47.67%
	Total	100%
Positive effects of confinement on relationship with confined people	Yes	44%
	No	56%
	Total	100%
Positive effects on social relationships	Yes	34%
	No	66%
	Total	100%
	None	31%
Negative effects on social relationships	Little	63%
	Some	5.33%
	Total	100%
	None	20.67%
	Little	29.33%
Positive effects on social relationships	some	44.67%
	great	5.33%
	total	100%
	total	100%

covid19. There are 31% people with no positive effects on social relationships, 63% participants having little positive effect on social relationships and 5.33% participants having some positive effect on social relationships. 20.67% participants have no negative effect on social life, 29.33% participants have little negative effect on social relationships, 44.67% participants have some negative effect and 5.33% participants have great negative effect on their social life.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

COVID19 has affected most people's lives worldwide. Due to the corona pandemic, the most hit listed people are students. Because of the corona lockdown they face a lot of stress and a lot of depression. Students face many of the problems due to corona lockdown because schools, colleges and universities are closed and their study system shifted to an online system. Due to that type of activity most of the students are affected by depression as there is no way to learn as they have before in the physical education system.

Recommendations

This study found that people had poor practices regarding corona pandemic. Most of the participants don't know the appropriate method to overcome stress regarding lockdown. My recommendation is that Senior Nurses should educate the participants about stress releasing methods.

Limitations

This study has limitations too. The sample size is small due to limited resources. As the sample size is small, its finding can't be generalized to the whole population.

REFERENCES

- Auerbach RP, Alonso J, Axinn WG, Cuijpers P, Ebert DD, Green JG, Mortier P (2016). Mental disorders among college students in the World Health Organization world mental health surveys. *Psychological medicine*, 46(14), 2955-2970.
- Bayram N, Bilgel N (2008). The prevalence and socio-demographic correlations of depression, anxiety and stress among a group of university students. *Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology*, 43(8), 667-672.
- Cao W, Fang Z, Hou G, Han M, Xu X, Dong J, Zheng J (2020). The psychological impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on college students in China. *Psychiatry research*, 112934.
- CNN (2020). Why the impact of corona virus could be particularly bad on college campuses. Retrieved from <https://edition.cnn.com/2020/03/07/health/universities-coronavirus-impact/index.html>.
- de Oliveira Araújo FJ, de Lima LSA, Cidade PIM, Nobre CB, Neto MLR (2020). Impact of Sars-Cov-2 And its reverberation in global higher education and mental health. *Psychiatry research*, 112977.
- Dosil-Santamaria M, Picaza-Gorrochategui M, Idoiaga-Mondragon N (2020). Esta solo es una vista previa 2 páginas mostradas de 10 páginas totales. *Cad. Saúde Pública*, 36(4), e00054020.
- Elias H, Ping WS, Abdullah MC (2011). Stress and academic achievement among undergraduate students in Universiti Putra Malaysia. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29, 646-655.
- FVG (2020). Webinar discusses education challenges during coronavirus pandemic. Retrieved from <https://portal.fgv.br/en/news/webinar-discusses-education-challenges-duringcoronavirus-pandemic>.
- Harvey D (2006). Neo-Liberalism as creative destruction. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography*, 88(2), 145-158.
- Kang L, Li Y, Hu S, Chen M, Yang C, Yang BX, Ma X (2020). The mental health of medical workers in Wuhan, China dealing with the 2019 novel coronavirus. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(3), e14.
- Karoly P, Ruehlman LS (2006). Psychological "resilience" and its correlates in chronic pain: findings from a national community sample. *Pain*, 123(1-2), 90-97.
- Li Z, Ge J, Yang M, Feng J, Qiao M, Jiang R, Wang L (2020). Vicarious traumatization in the general public, members, and non-members of medical teams aiding in COVID-19 control. *Brain, behavior, and immunity*.
- Medicine JHU (2020). Coronavirus COVID-19 global cases by the center for systems science and engineering at Johns Hopkins. [WWW Document]. Retrieved from URL [https:// coronavirus-jhu.edu/map.html](https://coronavirus-jhu.edu/map.html) (accessed 4.5.20)
- Odriozola-González, P., Planchuelo-Gómez, Á., Iruetia, M. J., & de Luis-García, R. (2020). Psychological effects of the COVID-19 outbreak and lockdown among students and workers of a Spanish university. *Psychiatry research*, 113108.
- Özdin S, Bayrak Özdin Ş (2020). Levels and predictors of anxiety, depression and health anxiety during COVID-19 pandemic in Turkish society: The importance of gender. *International J. Soc. Psychiatry*, 0020764020927051.
- Read, M. C. (2004). Effects of Quarantine. *Emerg Infect Dis*, 10(7), 1206-1212.
- Sahu P (2020). Closure of universities due to Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): impact on education and mental health of students and academic staff. *Cureus*, 12(4).
- Shigemura J, Ursano RJ, Morganstein JC, Kurosawa M, Benedek DM (2020). Public responses to the novel 2019 coronavirus (2019-nCoV) in Japan: Mental health consequences and target populations. *Psychiatry and clinical neurosciences*, 74(4), 281.
- UNESCO. (2020). COVID-19 educational disruption and response. Available at.
- Wang C, Pan R, Wan X, Tan Y, Xu L, Ho CS, Ho RC (2020). Immediate psychological responses and associated factors during the initial stage of the 2019 coronavirus disease (COVID-19) epidemic among the general population in China. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Pub. Health*, 17(5), 1729.
- Wang Y, Di Y, Ye J, Wei J, Wei R (2020). Study on the public psychological states and its related factors during the outbreak of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in some regions of China. *Psychology, Health & Medicine*, 1-10.
- Wu KK, Chan SK, Ma TM (2005). Posttraumatic stress, anxiety, and depression in survivors of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). *J. Traumatic Stress: Official Publication of The International Society for Traumatic Stress Studies*, 18(1), 39-42.

Zhai Y, Du X (2020). Addressing collegiate mental health amid COVID-19 pandemic. *Psychiatry research*, 113003.

Zhang Y, Ma ZF (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental health and quality of life among local residents in Liaoning Province, China: A cross-sectional study. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Pub. Health*, 17(7), 2381.

Zhou F, Yu T, Du R, Fan G, Liu Y, Liu Z, Gu X (2020). Clinical course and risk factors for mortality of adult inpatients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study. *The lancet*.

Zhu N, Zhang D, Wang W (2020). China Novel Coronavirus Investigating and Research Team. A novel coronavirus from patients with pneumonia in China, 2019 [published January 24]. *N Engl J Med*.